

SUPPLEMENTARY DOCUMENTS

Supplementary document 6. Associations between aortic wall thickness and hemodynamic parameters.

	Aortic layer vs Hemodynamic variable	Spearman r	p-value
FA/FA	Tunica intima vs SBP	0.0699	0.8346
	Tunica intima vs DBP	0.2098	0.5137
	Tunica intima vs HR	0.0839	0.8004
	Tunica media vs SBP	0.1748	0.5881
	Tunica media vs DBP	0.1818	0.5731
	Tunica media vs HR	-0.2098	0.5137
	Tunica adventitia vs SBP	0.6014	0.0428*
	Tunica adventitia vs DBP	-0.1259	0.6999
	Tunica adventitia vs HR	-0.0490	0.8861
FA/NFA	Tunica intima vs SBP	0.2028	0.5280
	Tunica intima vs DBP	-0.3018	0.3380
	Tunica intima vs HR	-0.2378	0.4573
	Tunica media vs SBP	0.7063	0.0129*
	Tunica media vs DBP	0.5719	0.0553
	Tunica media vs HR	0.2937	0.3545
	Tunica adventitia vs SBP	-0.7273	0.0096**
	Tunica adventitia vs DBP	-0.1754	0.5833
	Tunica adventitia vs HR	-0.3846	0.2183
NFA/FA	Tunica intima vs SBP	0.1368	0.6701
	Tunica intima vs DBP	-0.0947	0.7697
	Tunica intima vs HR	-0.2491	0.4319
	Tunica media vs SBP	-0.3497	0.2662
	Tunica media vs DBP	-0.1818	0.5731
	Tunica media vs HR	-0.2238	0.4851
	Tunica adventitia vs SBP	0.1608	0.6192
	Tunica adventitia vs DBP	0.2308	0.4708
	Tunica adventitia vs HR	-0.3916	0.2097
NFA/NFA	Tunica intima vs SBP	0.2175	0.4927

Tunica intima vs DBP	0.1121	0.7278
Tunica intima vs HR	0.4028	0.1941
Tunica media vs SBP	0.5009	0.0997
Tunica media vs DBP	-0.0699	0.8346
Tunica media vs HR	-0.0909	0.7830
Tunica adventitia vs SBP	0.2137	0.5021
Tunica adventitia vs DBP	0.0000	>0.9999
Tunica adventitia vs HR	-0.4266	0.1689
